

LEGAL STATUS OF THE PARTICIPANTS OF THE AIR CARRIAGE CONTRACT

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Abstract

Due to the nature and scope of the globalization process, it is more and more essential to move passengers using vehicles. Air transport contracts are subject to special legislation and need to be regulated independently.

The urgency of researching the legal status of subjects using air transport is also related to the transnationality of the issue, because the participants in the legal relationship represent states with different legal systems.

It is very important to determine the personality of the passenger at the legal level, in particular, the passenger can be only a natural person or also a legal person. The legislation of Georgia also does not contain an exhaustive legal regulation of the rights of the passenger/shipper. Thus, in order to avoid possible ambiguity and misunderstanding, it should be considered appropriate to discuss the issue from all sides.

The fact that our contract under consideration is distinguished from others by the so-called Duality In addition to the passenger, the cargo also appears in the contract, and the legal status of the recipient of the cargo is different from the legal status of the parties to the air transportation contract. In particular, he is a passive participant of the contract, he is not directly responsible for the proper performance of the contract.

Within the framework of the presented research, the analysis of the rights and duties of the entities involved in air transportation, the existing international standards in relation to this legal relationship, has been carried out.

Keywords: Air transport, passenger transportation, cargo transportation, transportation-carriage contract.

Introduction

One of the echoes of the globalization process in the modern world is the movement of people - from country to country, from city to city. Naturally, due to this, as a result of the transportation of passengers using a vehicle, the number of transportation-carriage contracts is significantly increased. The significant increase in the number of this type of agreements determines the relevance of the research question. In general, the transport system includes various types of transport, including air transport.¹ The air transport contract is characterized by a kind of specificity, which determines the need to subject it to special legislation and to regulate it independently.

Almost all issues related to air transport are transnational, and a number of states with different legal systems participate in related legal proceedings. Air transport is the safest form of transport, which leads to a significant increase in demand for its use. Air transport occupies one of the leading positions in the world, both in terms of passenger flows and circulation intensity.

Along with the increase in the importance of air transport, there is a need to research the legal status of subjects using the named transport.

Within the framework of the presented research, the rights and obligations of the subjects participating in air transportation, the analysis of the existing international standards in relation to this legal relationship will be carried out.

I. Status of the parties to the contract of carriage by air

1. Parties to the contract of carriage by air

The identification of the subjects participating in the air carriage-carriage contract acquires essential importance in terms of determining the responsible subjects in case of untimely fulfillment of the obligation and effectively protecting the right of the creditor. The subject of an air freight-carriage contract, like any other type of shipping-carriage contract, is the transportation of cargo to the place specified in the contract and its delivery to the consignee in exchange for the payment of the appropriate compensation.²

It is significant that the legal relationship arising from the contract of air carriage is regulated by both domestic and international legal acts. Among the domestic normative acts, the Civil Code of Georgia is worth noting, which regulates the relationship arising from the contract of carriage. The regulations established by the Civil Code are of a general nature and apply to all types of transportation contracts. The Air Code of Georgia is a special act regulating the relationship, which determines the basic requirements in the case of air transportation.

Among the international legal acts, the Convention "On International Civil Aviation" of 1944, which came into effect on April 4, 1947, is noteworthy. The mentioned convention acquires special importance in the process of development of international air law. The mentioned convention was ratified by the Parliament of Georgia on December 7, 1993.³

The Warsaw Convention of 1929 "On the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage and Carriage" and Additional Protocols belong to the important

¹ Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I, 2001, 311.

² Hopt K. J.; Kumpan, C.; Merkt, H.; Roth, M.; Baumbach, A., Kommentar zum Handelsgesetzbuch, Band 9, 36., Aufl., §407, 1502.

³ Geferidze D., International Air Law, 2009, 57.

act regulating the disputed issues related to the contract of air carriage. year "Warsaw system".

When considering the parties to the air carriage-contract, it is essential to separate the passenger and cargo carriage contracts from each other, since the status and legal status of the parties are regulated in completely different ways. In addition, in response to recent challenges in the country, in particular, in order to regulate the issue of paragliding and establish different rules for the operation of ultralight aircraft⁴, which, in turn, will contribute to the development of small aviation, the legislator made a number of changes in the legislation. In addition, according to the decree of the Government of Georgia on November 4, 2022 "On Implementation of Individual Measures to Ensure Public Safety", paragliding flights are prohibited in Georgia until the relevant legislation is adopted. In addition, specific measures were considered, which served for the further regulation of this field, although the analysis of the regulation of the issues related to the mentioned sprinklers will not be carried out within the scope of the presented research.

In general, in the case of a passenger transportation contract, one of the parties to the contract is the passenger. It is the manifestation of the will by the passenger that constitutes the basis for the emergence of the binding legal relationship (air carriage-contract) between the parties. The circle of persons who enjoy the status of passengers is not defined by the legislation⁵. Thus, the determination of the passenger's personality becomes essential, in particular, the passenger can be only a natural person, or also a legal person. Even in the absence of an unambiguous solution to the issue at the legislative level, the issue can be interpreted in such a way that only a natural person is considered a passenger.

The carrier is recognized as the other party to the passenger transportation contract. The transferor is an entity bearing rights and obligations recognized by domestic or international legal norms.⁶ The transferor can be both a natural person and a legal entity, although the aforementioned activities are usually carried out by legal entities⁷. In accordance with subsection "i1" of Article 1 of the Air Code of Georgia, an aircraft operator is a natural or legal person who operates an aircraft. In addition, the legislation establishes a number of requirements in the process of aircraft operation, which, in turn, is dictated by the need for safe operation and protection of the subjects participating in the agreement. In particular, it is required to have an operator's certificate, which, in accordance with Article 1 of the Air Code, subparagraph "i", is a document confirming the ability of the aircraft operator to safely operate the

aircraft, which is issued for commercial air transportation purposes.

When analyzing the status and legal status of the subjects participating in the air carriage-contract, it is necessary to focus on the legal status of the recipient of the cargo. In general, there is no consensus regarding the legal status of the consignee. It is significant that, despite not directly involving the consignee in the process of concluding the contract and being excluded from being considered a party to the contract on this basis, he appears as a participant in the proceedings, who is guaranteed by law a number of rights, including the possibility of submitting a request.⁸ According to a separate opinion, the sender and receiver of the cargo are considered as one party to the contract, however, the position that considers the air transportation contract as a transaction concluded in favor of a third party should be considered more justified⁹.

2. Rights and obligations of the passenger/shipper

The legislation of Georgia does not contain an exhaustive legal regulation of passenger/shipper rights. Thus, in order to avoid possible ambiguity and misunderstanding, it should be considered appropriate to discuss the issue from all sides.

2.1. The right to terminate the contract and refuse to fly

One of the passenger's rights is to terminate the air carriage contract and refuse the flight. Due to individual circumstances, it may be difficult for the passenger to fly. In order to protect the passenger's interests, the latter should have the right to request a refund of the paid fare. In such a case, the legal basis for protecting the passenger's interests is the first paragraph of Article 68 of the Air Code, which gives the passenger the right to refuse the flight and request the return of the paid amount. The only prerequisite for the implementation of the request under the named article is compliance with the deadline. Determination of the term, according to the principle of freedom to determine the content of the contract, depends on the manifestation of the will of the parties. Thus, the presented terms differ from each other and are determined in each specific case by the parties themselves. In case of violation of the notification period, the passenger does not lose the right to request a refund, however, in this case, according to Article 68, paragraph 2 of the Air Code, in case of late notification, the passenger has the right to recover part of the amount paid for transportation. The remaining amount (tax not to exceed 25% of the cost of the one-way transfer) is subject to withholding. The mentioned

⁴ In accordance with subsection "H31" of the first article of the Air Code of Georgia, an ultralight aircraft is an aircraft with no more than 2 seats and the maximum take-off weight of which does not exceed 600 kg when operating from the land surface, and - 650 kg when operating from the water surface.

⁵ Gabichvadze Sh., Civil legal regulation of cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air transport, 2012, 87.

⁶ Gabichvadze Sh., Grounds for civil liability and exemption from liability of the carrier by air transport according to the

legislation of Georgia, "Justice and Law" magazine No. 3, 2012, 76.

⁷ Gabichvadze Sh., Grounds for civil liability and exemption from liability of the carrier by air transport according to the legislation of Georgia, "Justice and Law" magazine No. 3, 2012, 97.

⁸ Hopt K. J.; Kumpan, C.; Merkt, H.; Roth, M.; Baumbach, A., Kommentar zum Handelsgesetzbuch, Band 9, 36., Aufl., §407, 1503.

⁹ Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I, 2001, 317.

norm serves to protect the passenger's interests. By limiting the amount of seized money to a threshold amount, the legislator established a norm protecting the passenger's interests. In such a case, determining the threshold amount serves to prevent abuse of the right by the carrier (considered the so-called "strong" party to the contract). It is significant that a similar regulation is provided by the Warsaw Convention of 1929 "On the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage by Air", according to which the passenger has the right to request a refund of the value of the travel document if the ticket is not used. The said right is revoked 30 days after the expiration of the ticket.¹⁰

2.2. Right to dispose of cargo

The sender has the right to dispose of the cargo sent by him. Disposition means giving specific instructions to the carrier of the cargo, which is mandatory for the carrier to fulfill. The carrier is not obliged to comply with the instructions of the sender in all cases. He can refuse to fulfill the instruction if it is objectively impossible to fulfill the instruction of the sender.¹¹ According to Article 680, Part 6 of the Civil Code, the carrier must immediately inform the sender about the impossibility of fulfilling the instruction. The shipper may not be given such an instruction that would lead to the division of the cargo, disrupting the normal production activities of the carrier. In addition, the sender does not have the authority to dispose of the cargo, when there is a direct reference in the bill of lading regarding the acquisition of the right to the cargo by the consignee¹². Article 12 of the 1999 Montreal Convention "On the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage by Air" establishes the following prerequisites for the sender to exercise the right to dispose of the cargo: the sender must provide the carrier with an instruction in writing; to reimburse the costs incurred as a result of cargo disposal; Compliance with the instruction should not prejudice the carrier; The carrier must be able to carry out the instruction objectively. Impossibility of fulfilling the instruction occurs when the carrier is unable to fulfill the instruction due to a specific defect.¹³ In the presence of the above-mentioned conditions, the sender has the possibility to enjoy the following right of disposal: request to send the cargo or return it to another specified airport; storage of cargo during transfer; transfer of the cargo to a person different from the one specified in the waybill at a specified place or on the way; Delivery of the cargo to the airport of dispatch by the carrier.¹⁴

2.3. The sender's obligation to provide information

The sender is obliged to provide the carrier with all the necessary information, which is necessary for the timely shipment of the cargo, and the data provided to the carrier must be correct. The sender should attach the mentioned data to the bill of lading and give it directly to the carrier. In addition, the carrier needs the information specified by the sender for the safe movement of the cargo at the customs border.¹⁵ According to Article 679, Part 2 of the Civil Code, the carrier is exempted from the obligation to verify the authenticity of the information submitted by the sender. Providing incorrect or incomplete information by the sender will result in legal consequences for the sender. However, the responsibility of the sender is excluded in case of the carrier's culpable act. The culpable action of the carrier may be manifested in the improper use or loss of the documents.¹⁶ According to Article 679, Part 3 of the Civil Code, the scope of liability of the carrier is limited in terms of quantity. In particular, the amount of the fine imposed on the carrier cannot be more than what the carrier would have been charged in case of cargo loss.

Article 6 of the 1999 Montreal Convention "On the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage by Air" establishes the obligation of the sender to provide data on the type of cargo before the request of the relevant authority. If the norms established by the customs, police or other authority provide for the obligation to provide such information, it is necessary to include them. This applies to e.g. Dangerous cargo or cargo that is subject to a state permit. (weapon, poison, etc.).¹⁷ Notices established by Article 6 of the Convention are addressed.

Article 6 of the Montreal Convention envisages the obligation of the shipper to provide the carrier with such information as: import permit, veterinary certificate, which is necessary for the fulfillment of contractual obligations during the transportation of cargo. Providing false and incomplete information entitles the carrier to claim damages. An additional compensation obligation may arise if the carrier has compensated a third party for damages or paid a customs or tax penalty. The responsibility of the sender does not arise when the carrier or a person authorized by him was himself guilty of the damage. e.g. The message sent by the sender was lost or etc.¹⁸

2.4. Obligation to pay compensation

Article 63 of the Air Code of Georgia specifies the payment of the established compensation as one of the main obligations of the passenger/shipper. The legislation of Georgia does not recognize the transportation of a passenger without payment of the appropriate fee. A person acquires the status of a passenger from the moment of purchasing the

¹⁰ Geferidze D., *International Air Law*, 2009, 303.

¹¹ Gabichvadze Sh., *Civil legal regulation of cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air transport*, 2012, 105.

¹² Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), *Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I*, 2001, 338.

¹³ Müller-Rostin W., *Das Recht des Luftverkehrs*, 29.

¹⁴ Müller-Rostin W., *Das Recht des Luftverkehrs*, 30.

¹⁵ Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), *Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I*, 2001, 336.

¹⁶ Gabichvadze Sh., *Civil legal regulation of cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air transport*, 2012, 108.

¹⁷ Müller-Rostin W., *Das Recht des Luftverkehrs*, 30.

¹⁸ Müller-Rostin W., *Das Recht des Luftverkehrs*, 30.

corresponding passenger ticket. Accordingly, it is subject to regulation established by legislation. In some cases, it is possible to transport passengers even without paying the required fare.¹⁹ The 1929 Warsaw Convention for the Unification of Certain Rules for International Carriage by Air recognizes free air carriage if the flight is operated by a certified air carrier.²⁰ Only the purchase of a ticket is not the basis for the emergence of rights and obligations, in addition, it is necessary for the passenger to report to the airport at the time specified in the passenger ticket and go through all the necessary procedures. Performing the named action leads to the possibility of granting the passenger status to the person.²¹ According to the 1929 Warsaw Convention "On the Unification of Certain Rules for International Carriage by Air", the passenger is responsible for compliance with the existing administrative, customs and sanitary rules for the flight. In addition, he must have all the travel documents necessary for the flight.²²

3. Rights and obligations of the carrier

3.1. The right to terminate the contract

Article 67 of the Air Code of Georgia gives the carrier the right to terminate the air carriage contract in the presence of special circumstances. In particular, if it is necessary to ensure the safety of the flight or to prevent the violation of the requirements of the legal normative acts of take-off, landing or overflight. The same result is associated with the performance of an action by a passenger that endangers the safety of the flight. The Warsaw Convention of 1929 "On the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage by Air" gives the carrier the right to refuse to carry cargo or to carry a passenger, and if a flight has already begun to continue it, if the operation of the flight would lead to a violation of the law, this is due to the protection of the interests of the passenger or the passenger by non-compliance with the instructions of the carrier²³. It is significant that the termination of the contract on the named basis creates a suitable legal instrument for the protection of the rights of both the carrier and the passenger. Taking into account the nature of the named grounds, in case of continuing to fulfill the obligation provided for in the agreement, the life and health of the passenger is at risk, which outweighs the interest of fulfilling the obligation provided for in the agreement.

3.2. Right to reimbursement of expenses

According to part 3 of Article 676 of the Civil Code, the carrier has the right to request compensation for the expenses incurred by the sender as a result of the sender's non-fulfilment of the obligation. If the subject of the contract of carriage is dangerous and the carrier

does not have information about it, he is entitled to destroy, as well as deliver this cargo without compensation for retaliatory damages. The carrier has the right to lien the subject matter of the air carriage contract to ensure reimbursement of the costs incurred.²⁴ A similar regulation is contained in the 1929 Warsaw Convention "On the Unification of Certain Rules for International Carriage by Air". In addition, the Warsaw Convention gives the carrier the right to request reimbursement of expenses from the passenger due to the violation of administrative rules.²⁵

4. Status and rights of the consignee

A contract of carriage of cargo is a contract concluded in favor of a third party in accordance with § 328 of the German Civil Code. The consignee is not a party to the contract of air carriage concluded between the consignor and the carrier, but in this case, according to a separate opinion, there is a contract concluded in favor of a third party. The receiver is not considered a party to the contract, although he has certain rights and obligations.

According to Article 681 of the Civil Code of Georgia, one of the rights of the consignee is the request that the second person hand over the bill of lading to him when the cargo is delivered. In addition, if the carrier fails to fulfill its obligations, from the moment of the delivery of the cargo, it has the right to submit a claim and reclamation against the carrier.²⁶ According to the Air Code of Georgia, the recipient has the right to refuse to accept the cargo if the cargo is damaged or spoiled and the possibility of using it for its intended purpose is reduced.

According to the 1999 Montreal Convention on the Unification of Certain Rules of International Carriage by Air, the consignee can request the carrier to hand over the bill of lading to him immediately, and he can also request that the cargo be handed over to him. Opposite to the right to transfer the cargo is the obligation to pay the amount, in the corresponding amount. The consignee is not obliged to pay additional costs, unless otherwise specified in the bill of lading. If it is mentioned about the advance payment, then the receiver is released from the obligation to pay the amount when submitting the cargo transfer request.²⁷

Conclusion

The analysis of the rights and obligations of the parties to the air carriage contract and the participant shows that the legal status of the recipient of the cargo is different from the legal status of the parties to the air carriage contract. In particular, he is a passive participant of the contract, he is not directly responsible for the proper performance of the contract. The contract of air transportation is mainly related to receiving a clear advantage for the recipient, although this applies

¹⁹ Gabichvadze Sh., Civil legal regulation of cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air transport, 2012, 88.

²⁰ Giemulla E., Luftverkehrsrecht, 8

²¹ Gabichvadze Sh., Civil legal regulation of cargo transportation and passenger transportation by air transport, 2012, 96.

²² Geferidze D., International Air Law, 2009, 303.

²³ Geferidze D., International Air Law, 2009, 303.

²⁴ Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I, 2001, 351.

²⁵ Geferidze D., International Air Law, 2009, 306.

²⁶ Zambakhidze T., Chanturia L. (ed.), Commentary on the Civil Code of Georgia, Book Four, Volume I, 2001, 343.

²⁷ Müller-Rostin W., Das Recht des Lufttransports, 32.

in the event that the sender and the recipient are different entities. In addition, it should be noted that in the presence of an airfreight contract, the receiver may also have an obligation to pay the amount, although his failure to fulfill this obligation is not related to any legal consequences. Unlike the parties to the contract of carriage, who are directly responsible for the proper performance of the contract and the legal consequences of failure to perform the contract.

It is obvious that when there is a consignee in the contract of carriage, there is a contract concluded in favor of a third party. The existence of a contract of carriage by air is related to receiving a specific benefit

for the recipient. When talking about the duties, it is necessary to distinguish that, unlike the legal status of the parties to the contract, the breach of the duty by the receiver is not related to the imposition of responsibility on him. However, on the other hand, the consignee acquires the right to the cargo from the moment of delivery and acquires the same rights that the sender would have had in his absence. This once again indicates that the party to the contract of carriage is generally only the bearer of a specific right, unlike the parties to the contract who are directly responsible for the proper performance of the contract.